

Historical Evolution of Islamic Law and its Application to Islamic Finance

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Abstract— Islamic Law or Shariah has come from the principles of the primary sources: Quran and Sunnah and is applied to the personal and public affairs of Muslims. Islamic law is deemed to be divine and furnishes a complete code of conduct based upon universal values to build honesty, trust, righteousness, piety, charity, and social justice.[1]

Islamic Jurisprudence primarily developed on the primary and secondary sources.[2] The establishment of four Sunni schools of Jurisprudence (Madhabs) occurred gradually over time and given distinct legal methodologies exhibiting their principle and mode of interpretation for deriving legal rulings.[3] The fundamental teachings of Islamic finance can be categorized in three distinct ways: prohibition of interest, guidelines on acceptable and permissible forms of contracts, and imposition of restriction on certain activities that are not in the interest of communities. [4] Islamic finance has imposed several restrictions to be followed in financial transactions guided by Sharia including the prohibition of Riba (usury), Gharar (uncertainty, deception, and risk), Gambling, and trade of forbidden commodities.[5] Islamic finance exhibited the outstanding potential to promote and support the execution plan of sustainable development goals (SDGs) introduced by the United Nations to establish and maintain human and environmental wellbeing.[6] Fintech solutions are developing fields to accelerate the digitalization of Islamic finance products and services for the harmonization of global investors mandate.[7]

The primary focus of this paper was to examine the development of Islamic jurisprudence (Fiqh) over time and its relevance to the field of Islamic finance. This encompassed a comprehensive analysis of the historical context, key legal principles, and their application in contemporary financial systems adhering to Islamic principles. This study aimed to elucidate the deep-rooted connection between Islamic law and finance, offering valuable insights for practitioners and policymakers in the Islamic finance sector. Understanding the historical context and legal underpinnings is crucial for ensuring the compliance and ethicality of modern financial systems adhering to Islamic principles. Fintech solutions are developing fields to accelerate the digitalization of Islamic finance products and services for the harmonization of global investors' mandate. Through this study, we focus on institutional governance that will improve Sharia compliance, efficiency, transparency in decision-making, and Islamic finance's contribution to humanity through the SDGs program.

The research paper employed an extensive literature review, historical analysis, examination of legal principles, and case studies to trace the evolution of Islamic law and its contemporary application in Islamic finance, providing a concise yet comprehensive understanding of this intricate relationship. Through these research methodologies, the aim was to provide a comprehensive and insightful exploration of the historical evolution of Islamic law and its relevance to contemporary Islamic finance, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of this unique and growing sector of the global financial industry.

Keywords— Sharia, Islamic principles, Sequencing Islamic jurisprudence, Islamic congruent Marketing, Social Development goals of Islamic Finance

INTRODUCTION

ISLAMIC Law also known as Sharia is a legal framework derived from the teaching of the Holy Quran and the Hadith of the Holy Prophet Muhammad. It focuses on all facets of life including the personal, social political, and economic activities of Muslims based on morality and integrity which are the cornerstones of Islam. Islamic code of conduct remains eternal. It is designed for all humanity to observe all places and always asserts to demonstrate good behavior. Fairness, social justice, respect, and honesty are important concepts in Islam that also apply to business dealings, and transactions, earning a good livelihood, and fair trading. The basic faith in Islam is to do good in an act of service to the divine with a clear intention in the heart.[8]

Indeed, in Islam, the inevitable and permissible affairs of life are transformed into acts of obedience if they are accompanied by noble intentions. Allah SWT, the Exalted and creator of the universe, established an order in the Holy Scriptures and sends Prophets to guide the people to live a good life on the right path. Among others, Islam is God's favorite and last religion. An Islamic society is based on brotherhood, empathy, kindness, and justice. The Quran gives clear instructions about the Divine commandment and set the rights, responsibilities, and rules for people and societies for compliance, such as the rights of Allah SWT (Haqqooq Ullah) and rights of man to man (Haqqooq ul Ibaad) [9]

The primary source of Islamic Law was completely founded during the Prophetic era which is obeying Allah and the Messenger. Holy Prophet Muhammad pbuh demonstrated these Divine messages, which are gathered in the hadith books to insight people for practical implementation of these principles in a society. After the demise of Prophet Muhammad, there was a need for Fuqaha (Islamic jurists) to decide on new legal matters where there is no such ruling in the Quran or the Hadith, Islamic Jurists apply a modus Operandi of interpretation, known as Usul-ul-Fiqh (principle of Islamic Jurisprudence), which is the total product of human efforts at understanding the divine will. Usul al-Fiqh relates to the principle and methodology of originating Islamic law.[10]

Islamic jurisprudence evolved by early Muslim scholars when they were working with primary sources concerning

authority and teaching linking theory and methodology. The Islamic Jurists undergo the adaptation and development of Islamic Jurisprudence to develop innovative theories and legal rules by employing the principle of Ijtihad, Maqasid al-Shariah, ethical and moral guidance, contextualizing and flexibility, integration of modern science and discipline to resolve the contemporary challenges being faced by the Muslim Ummah. Hence, the application of diverse approaches and interpretations allows the Islamic Jurisprudence for ongoing dialogue, discussion, and modernity to ensure that Islamic law stands always concerned, just, and applicable to the complexities of the modern world. The scholars like Muhammad Abduh, Rashid Rida, and Fazlur Rehman put modernized insight to meet the contemporary challenges and contexts. These approaches concentrated and emphasized flexibility, rationality, and reinterpretation of legal principles to derive legal rules to address contemporary issues.

Islamic law evolution is confronted with diversified knowledge and its interpretation due to having multiple schools of thought and differences of understanding. But you know This diversity can be seen as a strength, allowing for flexibility and adaptation, although it can also create challenges in achieving uniformity, standardization, corporate governance, education and awareness, and consistency in the industry.[11]

Business ethics in Islam are developed since the Prophetic era because of the importance of fairness and justice. Islamic marketing can equally be applied to Muslims and non-Muslims. The objective of Islamic marketing is not to generate money but rather aim to create benefits for the community while curtailing damages. Islamic Finance revolves to comply with Sharia's principle of business comprising profit-and-loss sharing partnership (Mudarabah), a joint venture called Musharakah, leasing (Ijarah), and investment products like equities and fixed-income schemes like Sukuk.[12]

Islamic finance is an emerging institution within the finance industry that derives its foundations from Islamic jurisprudence. The inspiration to launch Islamic finance was developed in 1970 to furnish a business platform for the billions of Muslims around the world for investing and accomplishing their financial concerns in guidance and compliance with Sharia. The causal impact of Islamic finance on the international market is keeping various perspectives, strengths, weaknesses, and potential areas of growth. The Muslim community is a religious pioneer in the halal industry and halal marketing. Islamic marketing targets to maximize stakeholder and community well-being by creating and executing principles enshrined in Quran and Sunnah. The main argument of Islamic finance is that some of the practices and principles that are used in conventional finance are strictly prohibited under Sharia laws such as interest, risk and uncertainty, speculation, and trading in prohibited activities. Consequently, Islamic finance is continuously growing to meet the rising challenges of the global financial system.[13]

Islamic Finance Development Indicator (IFDI) report published on December 15, 2022, mentioned that the Islamic finance industry reached almost US\$4.0 trillion in total assets in 2021, a growth of 17% from 2020. Also, the total global net

income of Islamic financial institutions increased by three times from 2020.[14]

Islamic law encourages the promotion of goods and restricts doing wrong for economic growth and the advancement of humanity. The Sharia asks for the eradication of poverty, hunger, and malnutrition from all members of society. Hence, Islamic Finance and sustainable or responsible investing have a great deal in common ensuring sustainable development goals (SDG) and taking care of society. Many of the tenets of Islamic Finance (IF) share the principles of responsible investing, presently looking forward to Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing.[15]

THESIS STATEMENT

The plain and instinctive purpose of this essay is to overview the Sharia interconnecting with the evolutionary process of Islamic Law. Ethical regulation of Islamic literature, research conducted on the Islamic business Market, ESG, Corporate Governance, and its importance to the Financial Institution and relationship of Islamic finance with the global financial market.

PRIMARY SOURCE

This paper is designed to collect the data from SOAS's library, JSTOR, and MLA recitation machine. The primary source will be Islamic Laws, Islamic Financial markets, and international research work. The secondary source will focus on the academic literature described in Islamic Jurisprudence, and Journal articles relating to the topic. Writing, footnotes, and bibliography would be styled under the OSCOLA form.

Objective: The objectives are to trace the historical evolution of Islamic law, its adaptation to contemporary Islamic finance, and its global impact, providing a comprehensive understanding of this significant intersection.

Methodology: This paper will give insight into a thematic approach for structuring a literature review of previous research work done on this sensitive area of study. This paper aims to use a qualitative method that is synthesizing the works to describe and correlate the true relationship of Sharia with Islamic finance. Exploring Islamic business ethics, ESG, and analyzing the modernity of Islamic financial law, and governance of financial institutions.

Limitation of research: The Islamic business prospect is a substantial area of study. Hence, the present initiative can build future studies in the Islamic jurisprudence of the Islamic financial system.

Implications for research and practice: As the study findings suggest, Islamic jurisprudence has evolved in different stages, and Islamic jurists and authors of embedded research work have provided different perspectives of Islamic law and marketing which interpretations differ from place to place. Therefore, future research needs to assess the different interpretations of Islam, and as such, their implications for Islamic finance complying with the standards and principles of Sharia.

Main Contribution:

This topic contributes by illuminating the profound historical roots of Islamic law, its integration into modern finance, ethical principles, enhancing comprehension of Islamic finance's unique ethical and financial framework.

2. Principle of Islamic Jurisprudence

Tauheed (monotheistic) is a fundamental concept of faith in Islam. Allah SWT is the only divine deity.[16] There are many verses of the Quran directing the believers, in one instance it is said “O believers! Obey Allah and obey the messenger and those in authority among you. Should you disagree on anything, then refer it to Allah and His Messenger, If you truly believe in Allah and the Last Day. This is the best fairest resolution”. Surah Al-Nisa (4:59). The Holy Prophet Muhammad is the most beautiful model. Islam expanded in Madina where the Companions of Prophet Muhammad increasingly had to resort to their repositories of knowledge. It was a time when Prophet Muhammad established the important tenet of ijihad.[17] Therefore, in the absence of the Holy Prophet, there were Companions with greater knowledge of the religion – such as Abu Bakr, Umar, ‘Uthman, ‘Ali, Ibn Masud, Muadh Ibn Jabal, ibn Ka’ab, Zayd bin Thabit, who were capable of ijihad and gave fatwa if something was not clear in the Quran or taught of Prophet (Sunnah).

Islamic Jurisprudence, also known as Fiqh in Arabic refers to the scholarly study and interpretation of Islamic law, which is derived from the primary source (Quran and Hadith) of Islam as well as secondary sources, containing the analogical reason (Qiyas) public interest (Maslaha) and Juristic preference (Istihsan) to address the new or unforeseen situation for which there might not have explicit narration in the primary sources.[18] It focuses on a comprehensive framework of legal principles, rules, and guidelines that control and direct the lives of Muslims in all spheres of personal conduct, worship, family affairs, business transaction, and criminal justice as well.

The classification and systemization of Islamic Jurisprudence (Usul-ul-Fiqh) were continuously relegated by numerous scholars over several centuries including four Sunni scholars as Abu Hanifah, Malik ibn Anas, Al-Shafi, Ahmad ibn Hanbal including the Shia scholar, Jafar al-Sadiq by formulating legal principles while categorizing legal issues for deriving legal rulings. Examples of these contributions include the “Muwatta” of Imam Malik and “Al-Risala of Imam al-Shafi. Moreover, various other prominent scholars such as Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani, Al-Ghazali, Ibn Taymiyyah, and Al-Shirazi have made significant contributions to the systemization and expansion of Fiqh literature.[19] The Islamic scholars organized the subject matter into various branches of Usul-ul-Fiqh such as acts of worship (Ibadat), transactions (Muamalat), family law, and so on.

Islamic Jurisprudence plays an important role in the legal systems of many Muslim societies and countries concerning their legal framework, personal status of law, constitutional recognition, family court and dispute resolution, civil and criminal law, judicial interpretation and legal reforms, and modernization. It is noteworthy, that some countries have mixed legal system that combines element of Islamic law with civil law or common law to create a balance between tradition and modernity.[20]

Modern scholars like Muhammad Abduh, Rashid Rida, and

Fazlur Rehman are focusing on a modernized insight to meet contemporary challenges and contexts. These approaches concentrated and emphasized flexibility, rationality, and reinterpretation of legal principles to derive legal rules to address contemporary issues.[21]

Here are brief explanatory descriptions of the sources of Islamic Jurisprudence:

1. Quran: the Quran is the primary source of Islamic law. Quran is said to be the words of Allah revealed on His last messenger Muhammad PBUH. Islamic Jurisprudence put top priority on the interpretation of rules and context between the line of Quranic verse and considered these as eternal and cannot deviate from the command of God.

2. Sunnah and Hadith: Sunnah means the action, statement, and approval of the Prophet Muhammad PBUM. It includes everything he said, did, and approved of. Hadith is a narration that records the Prophet's saying and actions handed down from the Companions of the Prophet. Islamic Jurisprudence relies on the Sunnah and Hadith as secondary sources of law and scholars analyzed the authenticity of Hadith to derive legal verdicts.

3. Ijma: (consensus): It is the third source of Islamic law, the universal and infallible agreement of Muslim scholars on specific legal issues. When there is unanimous agreement among the learned scholars, it reflects collective wisdom, and a ruling is considered binding and in case of difference of opinion it is not Ijma.

4. Qiyas (deductive analogy or reasoning): Qiyas is the analogical process of applying careful thought to the existing legal principle to deduce the rulings for contemporary issues that are not explicitly mentioned in the Holy Quran, Sunnah, and Ijma. Scholars focus on analogies between similar cases and apply proven legal ethos to deduce a legal understanding of the present situation.

5. Istihsan (Juristic Discretion): Istihsan is an Arabic term that refers to a juristic preference for a legal ruling that is "to consider something good". Muslim scholars may use it to express their preference for judgments in Islamic law over other possibilities. It allows flexibility in adopting Islamic law to contemporary issues to arrive at a suitable outcome. It is one of the principles of legal thought underlying scholarly interpretation or ijihad which is based on the principle of Maslaha (public interest).

6. Urf (Custom): Urf is considered a disputed secondary source; The principle of Urf connotes to be recurring practices and norms that are acceptable to people of sound nature and exclude having no benefit. Islamic Jurisprudence considered the social, cultural, and customary practices of a community that do not contradict established Islamic principles.

In the broad sense, the principle of Islamic Jurisprudence serves an important scope for interpreting and applying Islamic law and furnishing a structured approach to establish a legal ruling, maintaining the integrity of the legal tradition, adapting to changing circumstances, and equitable situations with contemporary requirements. Islamic Jurisprudence is pivotal for the evolution of the legal framework of Islamic Law.

2.1. Evolution of Islamic Jurisprudence

Islamic law is derived from the Quran and the teaching of the

prophet Mohammed PBUH. The Holy Quran manifests clear guidance about Divine order and described the rights, responsibilities, and rules for people and societies for compliance, such as dealing with Allah and man, and man to man.

Holy Prophet Muhammad pbuh exemplifies these Divine messages, which are recorded in the hadith books, showing people how he practically implemented these rules in a society. After the demise of Prophet Muhammad, there was a need for Fuqaha (Islamic jurists) to decide on new legal matters where there is no such ruling in the Quran or the Hadith, Islamic Jurists apply a modus operandi of interpretation, known as Usul-ul-Fiqh (principle of Islamic Jurisprudence), which is the total product of human efforts at understanding the divine will.[22]

The need for the development of Islamic jurisprudence emerged after the death of the Holy Prophet Muhammad and the following learned prominent seven Fuqaha of Madina endeavored to meditate on new legal issues which did not elucidate in the Quran and Hadith:[23]

1. Said ibn al-Musayyib.
2. Urwah ibn Zubair ibn al awwam
3. Salim ibn Abdullah ibn Umar
4. Qasim ibn Muhammad ibn Abi Bakr
5. Abu Salama ibn Abdur Rehman bin Awf
6. Suleyman ibn Yasar
7. Karajah ibn Zayd ibn Thabit.

Islamic Jurisprudence is well known as Fiqh which has been developed over time by Muslim Scholars and jurists such as Abu Hanifah, Malik ibn Anas, Al-Shafi, Ahmad ibn Hanbal and Shia scholar Jafar al-Sadiq and formulated legal principles by categorizing legal issues and deriving legal rulings. Furthermore, various other prominent scholars such as Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani, Al-Ghazali, Ibn Taymiyyah, Al-Shirazi, Syed Jalal Ud Din Afghani, Muhammad Abduh, Rashid Rida, and Fazlur Rehman have made significant contributions for systemization and expansion of Fiqh literature.

The evolution of Islamic Jurisprudence can be allocated into several periods according to their apparent characteristic and achievement.

The Fiqh traditionally developed into six major stages [24] known as Foundation, Establishment, Building, Flowering, Consolidation, and Stagnation and Decline, modern era as well These stages occur respectively in the following historical periods:

(a) Foundation era: (609-632 CE), The first stage in the development of Fiqh covers the era of the Prophet Muhammad ibn Abdallah's apostleship (609-632 CE) during which the only source of Islamic law was a divine revelation in the form of either the Quran or the Sunnah [the saying and actions of the Prophet (SAW) until 11 AHS.

(b) Establishment of Caliphs era, from the era of the Prophet: the era of the Righteous the death the Prophet (SW.) to the middle of the seventh century CE (632-661) second period "characterized by personal interpretations" of the canon by the Sahaaba or companions of Muhammad, lasting until 50 AH.

(c) Building era: from the founding of the Umayyad dynasty (661 CE, 51 AH) until its decline in the middle of the 8th century. There was a competition between "a traditionalist approach to jurisprudence" in Western Arabia where Islam was

revealed and a "rationalist approach in Iraq.

(d) Flowering era: from the rise of the 'Abbasid dynasty in the middle of the 8th century CE to the beginning of its decline around the middle of the 10th century. It is called the "golden age of classical Islamic jurisprudence" from the "early second to the mid-fourth century when the eight most significant schools of Sunni and Shia jurisprudence emerged.

(e) Consolidation era: the decline of the 'Abbasid dynasty from about 960 CE to the murder of the last 'Abbasid Caliph at the hands of the Mongols in the middle of the 13th century. from the mid-fourth century to the mid-seventh AH, Islamic jurisprudence was limited to elaborations within the main juristic schools.

(f) Stagnation and Decline era: The "dark age" of Islamic jurisprudence began from the fall of Baghdad in the mid-seventh AH to 1293 AH, (1258 CE to 1876 CE).

(g) Modern Era: In 1293 AH (1876 CE) the Ottomans codified Hanafi jurisprudence in the Majella el-Ahkam-i-Adliya. under "juristic revival movements" many jurists were influenced by exposure to Western legal and technological progress which continued till the mid-20th century. Muhammad Abduh and Abd El-Razzak El-Sanhuri were prominent Jurists of this era.

(h) Modern Era: The most recent era has been that of the "Islamic revival", which has been predicated on a rejection of Western social and legal advances and focused on the development of specific Islamic states, social sciences, economics, and finance.

It is noteworthy that Islamic Jurisprudence Continuously remained in the evolving process by the scholars to address contemporary issues and contexts. Islamic law evolution is confronted with diversified knowledge and its interpretation due to having multiple schools of thought (Madhabs) and differences of understanding. But this diversity can be visualized as a strength, allowing for flexibility and adaptation, although it can also create challenges in achieving uniformity, standardization, corporate governance, education, and awareness and consistency in the industry.

2.2. Rules of Interpretation

There are specialized rules of interpretation to emanate a legal ruling from the primary source of law in Islamic jurisprudence.[25] These support the scholars to understand the anticipated meaning of the Quran and Sunnah for application to legal issues under consideration. The most essential rules are:

1. Literal interpretation (Zahir): This principle involves understanding the text of the Quran and Hadith according to their apparent and linguistic meanings to build legal rulings directly from the explicit text.

2. Contextual Interpretation (Nass): It takes the visible context of verses of the Quran and Hadith to assimilate its intended meaning assuming its linguistic, historical, and social background when this verse was revealed.

3. Abrogation (Naskh): This principle applies to acquaint yourself with the present value of the verse that supersedes or abrogates the earlier rulings. The latter stands superior over the earlier in case of dispute to determine the presence of the explicit and valid reason for the abrogation.

4. Harmonization (Tawil): This principle involves the compatibility between two conflicting verses or Hadith through contextual analysis and linguistic reading to arrive at a coherent understanding within the overall legal framework.

5. Purpose and Objective (Maqasid al-Shariah): This principle focuses on the Maqasid al-shariah of Islamic law which allows for flexibility and adaptation to converging situations while respecting the core principle of Islam.

6. Precedents and Legal Analogy (Qiyas): This involves the application of knowledge between a known ruling and new contemporary issues to drive a legal ruling.

These above said rules of interpretation besides other principles such as consensus (Ijma), public interest (Maslaha), and custom (Urf) support scholars with tools and methodologies to understand and explain the primary source and driving legal rulings while keeping the originality of the text, historical background, and the Maqasid al-Shariah of Islamic Law.

2.3. VARIOUS MADHABS (SCHOOL OF THOUGHT)

The four Sunni schools of Jurisprudence (Madhabs) have been established over time and given distinct legal methodologies exhibiting their principles and interpretation for deriving new legal rulings required to address contemporary issues. There are also Shia (Jafri) Madhabs, and they follow a different set of legal principles and methodologies for deriving legal rulings based on the Quran, Sunnah, Imam's traditions, and Ijtihad. The Islamic scholars organized the subject matter into various branches of Usul-ul-Fiqh such as acts of worship (Ibadat), transactions (Muamalat), family law, etc. They relied upon legal traditions and methodologies within a broad perspective and framework of Islamic Jurisprudence and contributed richness and diversity to allow the application of Islamic law in different cultural, geographical, and historical contexts.[26]

Shia (Jafari School): Shia means a thought based on the teachings of the Prophet and his family, and sometimes it is referred to as the "school of Ahlal Bayt" followers as Shia of Ali. This school of thought was established by Imam Jafar ibn Muhammad al-Sadiq ibn Muhammad al-Baqir (700 or 702 to 765 CE), the sixth Imam. He refused to recognize the legitimacy of the Umayyad and Abbasid caliphs. Imam Jafar's teachings were laid down in 400 Usul (principles) incorporating the Hadith, Islamic philosophy, theology, Quranic verdict, Islamic literature, and ethics which were compiled by his students. It focuses on the analogy and fatwas of early Islamic jurists. The Jafari school is the main Shiite madhab and is practiced in Iran, Iraq, and partly in South Asia, Lebanon, and Saudi Arabia.

Hanafi Madhab: The Hanafi school of thought was established by Abu Hanifah al-Numan Ibn Thabit (700 to 767 CE). This school of thought was expanded by his disciple Abu Yusuf (died in 798). This is one of the Sunni Schools of thought and is considered the most moderate and flexible focused on reason and analogy. It is most favored and practiced by Sunnis in the Balkans, the Caucasus, Central Asia, China, Egypt, India,

Pakistan, Turkey, and large parts of the Arab world.

Hanbali Madhab: The Hanbali, a Sunni School of Thought was formed by Ahmad ibn Hanbal Ibn Taymiyyah ibn Aqil (780 to 855 CE) and is considered as most conservative and focused on selected texts initiated by the Wahhabi and Salafi branches. Saudi Arabia and the Taliban practice this school of thought.

Maliki Madhab: The Maliki Madhab (Sunni School) was founded in the 8th century by Imam Malik ibn Anas al-Asbah (715 to 795). This school dominates in North and sub-Saharan Africa, as well as in some parts of the Arab Gulf. This school considers only the consensus as a source of law derived by jurists of the seventh century of Medina, they believed that the people of Medina who lived there best preserved the traditions of the Prophet Mohammed PBUH.

Shafi Madhab: Shafi, a Sunni traditional School was established in the 9th century by Muhammad ibn Idris ibn al-Abbas, al-Imam al-Shafi (767–820 CE). This was the first school to systematize the sources of Islamic law in order of authority, with the Quran as superior, followed by the Sunna, this madhab is prevailing in Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Yemen, and some areas in the Middle East.

3. Modern Era of Islamic Law

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Middle Eastern rulers tried to modernize their states to compete more effectively with the European powers as it was the age of discoveries in science and technological advancements.[27]

The decline of the Ottoman Empire prompted the cultural, economic, and political sovereignty due to Christian occupation in the region led the Muslims of the Middle East to investigate whether their deprivation was in result of stagnancy in belief or political policies or inferiority of power. Islamic modernism is a religious reform to establish and meet the religious implication free from the shackles of orthodoxy that introduces reforms that trend it adaptable to the aggregate demands of modern society.

The modernization movement begins in the nineteenth century.[28]

Muslim reformers such as Syed Jalal al-Din Afghani (1838-1897) founding father of Islamic modernism.[29]

Muhammad 'Abduh (1849-1905), Rashid Rida (1865-1935), and others attempted to set a new path to introduce revolutionary concepts and ideas in all spheres of social, economic, and political affairs within the approaches that have wide compliance with the Sharia.

The Muslims were constrained to think either to adopt the Western ideology to modernize the Islamic system or to reject and put in protest and armed struggle against Western Power. Syed Jamal al-Din Afghani and his student Muhammad Abdu advocated Islamic modernism. They condemn the unquestioning acceptance (Taqlid) of Muslim scholars to their past and considered this responsible for the decline of Muslims. Nevertheless, some Islamic Scholars carefully have insight the Western colonialism and attributed it to the simple integration of the Jewish population.

Afghani advocated for an Islamic revival to unite the Muslim

community on the ideology of modern concepts even though confronting the cultural threat posed by the adaptation of Western philosophy. He blamed Western subjugation, not on Islamic inferiority, but the society's "intellectual backwardness" caused by the hundreds of years of neglect and suppression of the Islamic umma, or community. Afghani also blamed the influence of Sufism, which led to passivity, fatalism, and spiritualism, and deprived them of thinking about innovation. Some scholars fixed the responsibility of the Mongol Empire's domination for replacing early Islamic intellectual progress with sentimental legends.

Syed Jamal al-din Afghani contended that values lost by Muslims during the domination could be evaded by the adoption and reclaiming of modernism in Islamic Society as there existed no dichotomy between religion and science. Afghani stressed that in addition to studying their religion, Muslims should formulate new responses to the changing societies out of the Islamic principles they learned in their studies. He emphasizes that Muslims could use Western ideology to their advantage. Hence, those ideas should be studied to compete for world challenges.

The Modernism exponent stressed that Muslims must be taught to give an understanding of modern science and philosophy, including modern social and political philosophies. Jamal al-Afghani iterated those secularizing tendencies shaped by capitalist processes.

Muhammad Abduh (1849-1905) [30] believes in natural law that promotes humanity in the complaint of command of Allah SWT.

Abduh embraced the thought of modernity where the individual should distinguish right or wrong to live their life in the modern age by avoiding undermining their religious belief. The fundamental concept proposed by him was largely grounded in rationalism, liberalism, nationalism, and the universalism of Islam. His work and struggle have brought an unprecedented change in the legal, social, and political structure of Egypt, and helped to revitalize modern Islamic aspirations.

Rashid Rida was a Syrian Islamic reformer of the 20th century.[31] who promoted the methodology of interpretation of Islamic law to address the issues of modernity. Rida advocated that Mujtahids should take a broad view of all considerations affecting public interest; not merely 'take the example set by the Prophet in all its particulars even when this obliges them to ignore the public interest and the textual limit must be respected.

Rida was critical of rigid religious authorities, as well as reformers who encouraged a European model of secularization, he was neither a conservative nor a liberal. He was merely a Muslim reformer. He argued that Ibadat (worship) should be observed in total compliance with Sharia otherwise it will be treated as a new religion. The jurist should adhere to the principle of Usul al-Fiqh defining the (Muamalat) affairs under question while applying the true spirit of qiyas Istihsan.

The Ottoman modernization process started in the 19th and early 20th centuries and accelerated during the Tanzimat era [32] with juridical, political, and economic reforms in compliance with Sharia that aimed not identical to the changes

in Europe. Under the Tanzimat reforms, many legal Acts and procedures were promulgated from 1839 to 1876. Vis-a-vis Commercial Code 1850, Penal Code 1858, code of commercial procedure 1861, code of Maritime Commerce 1863, and Majella 1876.

The role of Qadi was important. Qadi, an Islamic judge must have good character and Islamic knowledge. The Qazi's Ordinance of 1856,[33] recommended mufti be consulted and the sentences of qadis were checked by the court-appointed Muftis until 1880 when the Sharia Courts Ordinance was promulgated introducing the hierarchical judiciary. The individual or parties were allowed to assail appeal in the Cairo Sharia court against Qadi's decisions.

Sultan Abdulmecid I (1823-1861) in 1839,[34] regulated the edict of Culhane in the Tanzimat reform of state to administrate the contract between rulers and ruled and provide a rule of law for all subjects by guaranteeing life and property rights. The case of every accused party will be tried publicly, in conformity with our divine law. The Culhane ruling created a taxation system through employed tax collectors instead of tax farming and imposed a ban on the unwanted recruitment of military forces within administrative districts. The Ottoman rule ended a Kul system that allows the confiscation of a public servant's property at the desires and wishes of rulers.

New Arab nation-states renewed their efforts at modernizing their respective laws and judiciaries pursuing the French and British Mandate. Egypt was the pioneer of this process through the work of the French-educated Egyptian jurist, 'Abd al-Razzaq al-Sanhuri a member of all three legislative committees was designated for the revision of the Egyptian Code in 1930. Sanhuri developed a reformist agenda by conceptualizing Egypt's law in a more progressive and egalitarian way. He modernized Islamic law by "applying the insights of sociological critiques of classical legal thought." His scholarship was motivated by a desire to balance and develop the Ottoman codifications of Islamic law with modern positivist conceptions of law inspired by the West (primarily from Swiss, French, English, and American laws). Sanhuri believed that Islamic law and Western laws were not antithetical. Rather, Islamic law had a "contemporary relevance in other than a fundamentalist or recidivistic sense".[35]

4. Islamic Socio-Economic and Characteristic

Allah, the Exalted and creator of all things, enshrines and gives a divine order in Holy Scriptures and sends Prophets to guide us to live a good life. We cannot be strayed if we follow the principles and guidelines of Islam, those provide us with an ethical and moral code and improve our sense of responsibility and accountability in all spheres of life including business dealing. The keystone of Islam is that do what is permissible and refrain from that are forbidden. Quran and the traditions of Prophet Muhammad hold many quotations about the trade that directs how to conduct business.[36]

Prophet Muhammad emphasizes honesty and kindness in all business transactions. He said an honest and trustworthy merchant will be raised with the Prophets, the truthful, and the martyrs. Jabir (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the

Prophet of Allah PBUH said: "May Allah have mercy on a man who is lenient when he sells, and when he buys, and when he demands back his money."

Prophet Muhammad admonished the marketplace trick of telling people a higher price of a commodity for bargaining to raise the price and increase the sale. The Prophet forbade the traders to demonstrate righteousness, and honesty in business dealing and to give charity to deserving people. Similarly, if you are dishonest and unjust in your business dealings, then you are distancing yourself from Allah's Mercy. Hence, Islamic economics focuses on morality, sympathy, equity, and equality to implement the commands and rules of the Shariah to avoid injustice in acquiring and utilization of material resources to promote humanity as well as performing the obligations to Allah and society.[37]

4.1. Principle of Islamic Economics

The Islamic economic system operates differently from the conventional economic system in just of their concepts or ideologies. The principle of Islamic economic works under Islamic teaching and furnish a framework for economic activities that coincide with Islamic principle and values.[38]

1. Prohibition of Riba (interest): This is an important principle of Islamic economies that forbids charging or paying interest on loans or financial transactions being unjust and exploitative arrangements. Islamic financing encourages profit-sharing and risk-sharing provisions that promote fairness and equitable distribution of wealth.

2. Prohibition of Gharar (Uncertainty): Islamic economies encourage clarity, transparency, and amicable agreement to ensure fair and ethical economic dealing and discourage transactions that involve uncertainty or ambiguity (Gharar).

3. Prohibition of Haram (Illegal) Activities: Islam has set rules about Halal activities and is directed to forbid unlawful activities which are harmful to society such as the use of alcohol, pork, gambling, and other prohibited goods and services.

4. Distribution of Zakat (Charity): Islam emphasizes the deduction of zakat from wealth at a certain period and percentage that is mandatory and obligatory to support the less fortunate and specific categories of people in society.

5. Promote Equity and Equitable Transaction: Islamic finance promotes economic cooperation and mutual usefulness by encouraging financial transactions that are based on fairness, justice, and ethical conduct and forbid exploitative monopolies, and unfair market practices.

6. Promote Productive Economic Activities: Islamic finance encourages productive economic activities that contribute to the well-being of an individual and society at large. It focuses on sustainable development through productive investment and discourages economic transactions that depend on speculation, uncertainty, and unearned income.

7. Ensuring Property Rights: Islamic economics encourages the acquisition and accumulation of wealth through lawful business and activities focusing on the sense of social responsibility and redistribution of wealth under the guidance of Islamic principles.

Overall, the principles of Islamic economies emphasize building an equitable and conducive economic system for the well-being of individuals and society. These principles provide a moral and ethical framework to harmonize responsible entrepreneurship, wealth distribution, and fair market practice to promote economic justice and social welfare.

5. Global Islamic Marketing System Plan

Islam is a path of life directing Muslims in every facet of life including all business and marketing activities for attaining human welfare. Islamic finance is an emerging department within the finance industry that derives its foundations from Islamic jurisprudence. The inspiration to launch Islamic finance was evolved in 1970 to furnish a platform for the billions of Muslims around the world to invest and carry out their financial matters in guidance of as well as compliance with Sharia.[39]

The development of a global Islamic marketing system plan is concerned with making unique characteristics and adaptability of Islamic market strategies in compliance with Islamic principles. Here are some essential components encompasses in the global Islamic marketing plan:[40]

1. Market Analysis: The most important element of impact investing is conducting a thorough analysis of the global Islamic market to identify demographical consumer preference, size and potential growth, and cultural value that influence purchasing options and decisions relating to your brand and services. Ozlem Sandikci Is a prominent scholar in the field of consumer behavior and Islamic marketing who explore the intersection of Islam, consumption, and marketing and she has published numerous articles in academic journals.[41]

2. Islamic Brand opportunity: After exploring the Islamic market, it follows the brand identity, selecting a brand name, logo, and visual identity attracting targeted consumers aligned with Islamic ethics. Paul Temporal is an expert in Islamic branding and marketing and created global Islamic Business and Branding in Asia.[42]

3. Halal Product Certification: For authentication of a halal product, it is mandatory to obtain halal certification from the competent authority to satisfy the consumers that the product meet Islamic dietary requirement and produces according to Islamic principles. Dr. Jonathan AJ. Wilson, El-Bassiouny Hisham, and Dr. Dina Ahmed Zidan are prominent scholars who made extensive work on the global halal industry they also focus on understanding consumer behavior in the Muslim market, and they have developed effective market strategies.[43]

4. Product Development: It is the golden strategy of the market that products, packages, and services must be reshaped and modified according to the requirement of consumers by considering Islamic ethics and principles. Jonathan Liu is an expert on the marketing influence of Islamic values and the importance of cultural sensitivity particularly halal food, branding, and tourism in reaching Muslim consumers.

5. Consumer's Interaction: The market communication strategies must be created and aligned to Islamic values and useful for the product and services by using appropriate friendly websites and utilizing electronic and social media for digital

advertising outreach to a targeted audience.

6. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR): It stands imperative to integrate socially responsible activities into the market plan corresponding to the Islamic principle of philanthropy and societal welfare to build trust and loyalty among the target consumers.

7. Effective Coordination: It is necessary to make a strategic partnership with Islamic institutions and businesses to increase market reach and credibility through coordination on the joint market campaign, event, and sponsorship that correspond with Islamic ethics and resonate with the target audience.

8. Perpetual Assessment and Adoption: It is an important activity to regularly revisit the effectiveness of marketing strategies and tactics by monitoring the market trend, consumer feedback, and emerging opportunities for changing and adopting marketing strategies to meet consumer preferences and maintain a competitive thrust in the global Islamic market.

Under the given description, the Islamic marketing system can be tailored for adaptation and development that resonate with Muslim consumers and foster brand loyalty for attaining business growth.

5.1. Challenges to Halal Marketing

The Muslim community is a religious pioneer in the halal industry and halal marketing. Muslim marketer understands that Islamic principles should not be breached in manufacturing product and service and must not entail any element prohibited in the Islam Halal market concentrating on promoting and selling halal product and relevant services that comply with Islamic dietary and ethical requirements. As a result, face several challenges concerning the region, market, and specific industry reported three major barriers to the practice of halal marketing.[44] These include “harmonization of standards; information scarcity and industrial innovation challenges”. In terms of harmonization, they report the existence of multiple interpretations of halal in the diverse Muslim community creating confusion for firms looking to approach the halal market. Furthermore, the absence of uniform halal certification and logo also creates a problem for firms engaged in global supply chains or exporting to various countries.

Secondly, lack of information and awareness affects suppliers in terms of opportunities available in the market, and consumers, about the existence of a halal category of products as the consumer is not fully understood what the dietary plan of a halal product is.

The final barrier for the halal industry which is fragmented by the diverse cultural, linguistic, and regulatory environment affecting efficiency is whether the industry can create new value and new satisfaction for the customer. The supply chain and cost considerations are also big challenges to the Halal market. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) may confront the challenging threat to bear the additional costs and overhead while limiting their ability to enter the halal market.

Overcoming these challenges demands a strategic approach that builds the trust of consumers through authentic certification, creating outreach, conducting field investigations, effectively supply chain, and tailoring marketing strategies to

specific markets, corporate governance, and realization of corporate social responsibility can handle and navigate the challenges of halal marketing.

6. Merging Impact of Islamic Finance on Sustainable Investment:

The pandemic Covid-19 exacerbated the huge financing gap notably in the economy of developing countries by reducing the external financing of USD 700 billion in 2020. According to the OECD’s report, the annual SDG financing gap in developing countries increased to USD 4.2 trillion in 2020. Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, governments were facing a USD 2.5 trillion annual financial gap for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Hence, Islamic finance can hold a fund of financing for the SDGs, having total assets of USD 4 trillion in 2022 with a projected aggregate growth rate of 8% per annum until 2025.[45] Thus, reallocating 1% of global capital to the SDGs would be sufficient to fill the gap, but this requires the effective use of available resources and the exploration of innovative sources of funding for the SDGs. Substantial financing is required to respond to today's sustainable development challenges of poverty, social inequality, and environmental degradation, which exceed the capacities of governments to solve.

Islamic finance having ethical and socially responsible principles might have a significant impact on sustainable investment. Islamic finance discourages investment in sectors treated to be unethical and unlawful that are harmful to society and encourages a structured framework for incorporating ethical investment criteria into investment decision-making.

Islamic finance focuses on the environmental and social factors of investment decisions. The Islamic economic principle such as forbidding excessive risk (Gharar) and promoting social welfare (Maslahah) essentialize the assessment of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in every impact investment. Hence, Islamic Financial Institutions (IFI) are considering ESG criteria in their investment, policies, corporate governance, and responsible investing.

Consequently, Islamic finance made a pivotal role in financing renewable energy projects and clean technologies such as solar and wind power. IFI has developed innovative financial products like green sukuk (Islamic Bond) to fund renewable energy and environmentally friendly projects.

Additionally, Islamic finance is gripped on impact investing which focuses on ESG along with financial return. Islamic Financial Institutions have started a specialized fund for promoting social welfare, like affordable housing, healthcare, education, and microfinance. Moreover, Islamic finance encourages investment in real assets and productive economic activities instead of short-term or speculative transactions.

Islamic finance implements international standards of accounting and auditing and emphasizes transparency, accountability, and good governance in financial transactions. IFI's commitment to corporate governance increases its sustainability and achievement of sustainable investment.

So, the impact financing made by Islamic finance is evident

in the growing number of IFI adopting sustainability framework, offering green financing, and establishing ESG consideration in their investment plan. The convergence between Islamic finance and sustainable investment enhances growth and development in the global financial system.

6.1. Standardization of Islamic Finance for International Adoption:

Harmonization in Islamic finance practices and the adoption of global best practices have enabled Islamic finance to be recognized by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) as systemically important in over 14 jurisdictions and is now offered by more than 300 financial institutions across 60 countries.[46]

The efforts of financial institutions have largely reduced the possibilities in the interpretation and practice of Shariah principles to ensure the soundness, stability, and integrity of the Islamic finance industry. Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) is entrusted to provide governance and disclosure information required for Shariah-compliant institutions. Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) delivers a standardization of Shariah rules for the implementation of Shariah contracts and financial transactions. International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM) furnishes standardization of contracts in key areas such as risk participation, interbank transactions, and money markets. Despite this, stringent efforts are diverted to homogenize industry practices to drive a set of globally accepted standards.

The financial institutions to raise clarity needs an Islamic ruling or Fatwa issued by a recognized authority of Islamic scholar to present legal guidance and greater assurance of Shariah compliance among stakeholders within a transaction. Hence, Uniform standards will increase the scalability of services, and industry efficiencies and enhance public confidence as well as increase cross-border marketability, transparency, and consistency in financial reporting. The Regulators of Financial Industries are constantly aware of the importance of developing an international, comprehensive, and more structured legislative framework for Islamic finance to accelerate growth and reduce anomalies around the world.

6.2. Global Islamic Finance and Impact Investing Platform (GIFIIP):

The United Nations Development Program held in Istanbul International Center for Private Sector in Development and Islamic Development Bank established the Global Islamic Finance and Impact Investing Platform (GIFIIP) in 2016 to promote Islamic finance and impact investing for the implementation of global SDG by engaging the private sector, governments, and key stakeholders operating in the Islamic finance and impact investing markets. The Platform promotes market-based solutions to sustainable development challenges by creating collaborative working among the actors.[47]

CONCLUSION

The Aqedah Tauheed (monotheism) is a pivotal of Islamic Finance realizing the belief that every provision to the creature

is bestowed from Allah and that is the foundation of economic sustainability. The Islamic financial system is based on social justice and focuses on humanity. The Islamic jurisprudence is continuously evolving, and Islamic Jurist is endeavoring to meet the contemporary challenges of the global financial system by using a consensual approach and facilitating logical thinking emphasizes Ijma (Consensus), Qiyas (Analogy), and Ijtihad (Independent Reasoning). Islam intends to find a balance between commercialism and humanitarianism as well as profit and social responsibility.

Islamic Jurisprudence plays an important role in the legal systems of many Muslim societies and countries concerning their legal framework, personal status of law, constitutional recognition, family court and dispute resolution, civil and criminal law, judicial interpretation and legal reforms, and modernization.

Islamic finance has gained significant importance in the world due to its potential growth, extensive acceptance, suitability to financial challenges, exclusiveness to speculation, and prohibition of riba (interest). The pandemic of Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) exacerbated the huge financing gap notably in the economy of developing countries. Substantial financing is required to respond to today's sustainable development challenges of poverty, social inequality, and environmental degradation, which exceed the capacities of governments to solve. Even before Covid-19, governments were facing a USD 2.5 trillion annual financing gap to meet the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Islam teaches us about the protection of the environment and the nourishment of human civilization. The environment is presently more fragile and warrants the attention of every individual to work actively to avoid destruction. Consequently, investing for impact, sustainability, socially responsible investing, and green investment fall within the purview of Shariah-complaint investment.

Islamic finance has always supported purposeful and useful investments, and now the ethical aspects of social impact are becoming more important. Financial institutions need to raise uniform standards to increase the scalability of services, industry efficiencies and enhance public confidence as well as increase cross-border marketability, transparency, and consistency in financial reporting. Thus, warrant a structured legislative framework for Islamic finance to accelerate growth and reduce anomalies around the world.

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